

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: ACHOLA****FIRST NAME: KEVIN****PROGRAM CODE: DEOH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: PR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 2%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

CREATING PH.D. QUIZZES

1. While searching for a topic for essay writing, understanding the topic is key through detailed reading while asking specific critical questions in the reader's mind. Which of the following is a key question about this context?
 - What do you already know about the topic?
 - What do you need to read and know to write the essay?
 - Are these materials functional to my topic or argument?
 - All of the above.**¹

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, Fifth Edition (Washington, DC: Euclid University Press, 2024), 8.

2. Essay writing requires both creative and critical thinking. One of the statements is true about creative and critical thinking.
- Creative thinking encourages you to broaden your ideas and involves techniques such as brainstorming and mind-mapping.²**
 - Your essay should not be balanced to include a range of information and viewpoints from different authors.
 - Only include evidence that agrees with what you are arguing.
 - Evaluate only two differing arguments.
3. When handing in your essay, it is essential to ensure that
- You can submit your essay in plastic folders or sleeves.
 - Your essay is formatted correctly.³**
 - You can print on both sides of the page.
 - Your essay is stapled in the top right-hand corner and keep an extra copy of the document for yourself.
4. Which of the following in all research projects serves as the aim
- To ask questions worth answering.
 - To find answers, you can use reliable evidence to support your reasons.
 - To find good data that you can use as reliable evidence to support your reasons.

² Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, 9.

³ Ibid., 12.

All of the above.⁴

5. Below, which approach could researchers use to develop research topics/questions?

- Answering only questions that others in their field want to answer.
- Do not begin with basic curiosity, a vague intellectual itch that needs scratching.
- Questions that pop into a researcher's mind with no hint of where they will lead to, sometimes on matters so seemingly trivial that only the researchers think they are worth answering.**⁵
- Shying from cultivating the ability to see what is good in commonplace.

6. In questioning your intended research topic, self-queries could include

- Ask how the topic fits into a focused area with only historical contexts always being considered.
- Turn positive questions into positive answers.
- There is no room for speculative questions.
- Ask questions that build on disagreements.**⁶

7. Secondary sources of literature serve the following purpose

- To keep up with current research.
- To find other points of view.

⁴ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers and Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers* (Chicago and London: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 23.

⁵ Ibid., 24-25.

⁶ Ibid., 26-27.

To find models for your research and analysis.

All the above.⁷

8. A schema is an abstract structure of information that helps the researcher to organize, remember, and use information during the writing process. The following statement is true about a schema in research writing.

In schema specialization, concepts are compacted into one part.

In schema generalization, concrete concepts are broken into several parts with specific schemata connected to derive a higher-order schema.

A procedural schema helps the learner understand the steps necessary to complete a complex task.⁸

A procedural schema is not necessarily essential in understanding the relationships among the dissertation sections.

9. To ensure that the literature review provides an adequate foundation for the research questions

Structure the paragraphs to build the argument for answering the research arguments.

At this stage, all the terminology will be defined for the reader later.

Include value judgments.

⁷ Kate L. Turabian, 36.

⁸ James P. Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research: Dissertation Research Guide* (Tallahassee: Florida State University Press, 2017), 16-17.

- Include a summary of complicated sections of the review.**⁹

10. The WHO recommends the use of the following descriptions

- People with physical disabilities.**¹⁰
- The elderly.
- The physically handicapped.
- The vibrant people.

⁹ James P. Sampson, 32.

¹⁰ World Health Organization, *Style Guide* (Geneva: World Health Organization Press, 2013), 55-58.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, Fifth Edition. Washington, DC: Euclid University Press, 2024.

Turabian, L. Kate. *A Manual for Writers and Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Chicago and London: The University of Chicago Press, 2018.

Sampson, P. James. *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research: Dissertation Research Guide*. Tallahassee: Florida State University Press, 2017.

World Health Organization. *Style Guide*. Geneva: World Health Organization Press, 2013.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.